

Towards Clustering Technique for a Fault Tolerance Mobile Agent-Based System in Wireless Sensor Networks

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ABSTRACT

The inherent problems of client/server model of networking has been reasonably minimized by the emergence of mobile agent (MA) computing paradigm. Reliability is a major priority in any energy constrained networks. This paper adopts clustering algorithm and mobile agent technology to propose a reliable and energy-efficient data transmission to improve the life span of wireless sensor networks. The primary advantage of cluster-based architecture is that it requires less transmission power due to small communication ranges within the cluster. The subsequent simulation of the proposed algorithm in further studies will be compared with other techniques and Leach Energy Adaptive Clustering Hierarchy (LEACH) protocol and its stability over the existing LEACH protocol and other techniques will be validated in terms of lifetime and energy consumption.

KEYWORDS

Fault Tolerance, Mobile Agents, Clustering, Sensors, Wireless Networks, Cluster Heads

1. INTRODUCTION

Continuous developments in the area of microelectronics and wireless communications has attracted the attention of researchers in recent times. These advancements have led to the development of micro size, low-cost, low-powered and multifunctional sensor nodes that can communicate over short distances in an ad-hoc way. [1] noted that energy efficiency remains a critical issue when it comes to data dissemination in wireless sensor networks. Generally, sensor nodes are limited in computing and communication power. Applications of wireless sensor networks have been discovered in industries, the fields of healthcare, military, environmental monitoring, farming, disaster management and many more.

Deploying Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) in critical environments requires a high degree of dependability. Availability, reliability and maintainability are features that wireless sensor networks must satisfy before it can be considered dependable. Service level availability means that WSN is able to provide the intended services even though the network encountered failures in any of its components such as single nodes or node subsystems. Availability to a large extent depends on fault tolerance to keep the system working as expected. [2]. Maintainability is a feature of a system that provides for continuous adjustments and modifications after the initial deployment for enhanced and longer service delivery. It shows the confidence and quality in the operations of a system.

Clustering is widely considered and adopted as energy-efficient technique in WSNs. Cluster-based routing technique requires extra resources on the CHs since they are responsible for the collection of data from their cluster members and forwarding of data to the sink [3].

To reduce energy consumption in sensor nodes, [4] adopted the rotation of CH's role method in the clustering protocols. [5] proposed the use of sensor nodes with high energy to act as CHs, however, there still exist the problem of fast energy depletion of these nodes since they are powered with non-rechargeable and non-replaceable batteries once deployed. Therefore, the limited energy can be maximized through the adoption of clustering protocol to avoid early death of the WSN.

[6] reported an energy saving routing protocol for cluster based WSNs. The algorithm works on the principle of powerful cluster head (CH) selection, residual energy of the CHs and the intra-cluster distance for cluster formation. Nodes advertise to become cluster head by initiating a time delay which depends on its residual energy. Other nodes decide to join CHs by considering their residual energy and transmission range to the CHs.

Faults in wireless sensor networks occur for so many reasons such as low energy level, malicious attacks and software and hardware failures. Communication links and limited resources can also lead to network failure.

Redundancy is removed from the sensory data through aggregation by the mobile agents and clustering is used to reduce flooding. We propose formation of clusters in the deployment of wireless sensor networks. In every cluster, cluster head is selected. The CH plays a crucial routing role as it serves as the medium for all the cluster members to transmit the sensory data to the processing. Since members do not directly transmit data to the sink node, member nodes can save energy utilization through the assistance of the CHs. However, there are possibilities of failures in the CHs that is why we introduced the concept of mobile agents to be assigned to each cluster head to handle such failures. Mobile agents are autonomous with the ability to continue from where it stops in data acquisition and processing in the event of network failure. Mobile agents provide energy awareness, reliability, scalability, and extensibility.

A fault tolerance system is a system that still provides the original services in the presence of logical errors. It is achieved with special algorithms or additional components.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

In this section, sources of faults in wireless sensor networks, clustering in wireless sensor networks, and reviews of related works are investigated.

2.1 Source of Faults in Real WSN Applications

In any data gathering and reporting systems that is serviced by a network, if the application in the back-end which presents the WSN data to the network users suffers a fault due to some failures, the entire system is considered faulty.

In any wireless sensor networks, a failing node can cause the entire network to fail. For example, if the node is on a routing path, the fused messages of other nodes relying on this routing path will not be delivered rendering the entire network inactive.

- 1) **Node Faults:** Nodes have several hardware and software components that can produce malfunctions. A data acquisition application will not perform properly if the underlying sensors provide incorrect readings. However, some hardware failures do not affect all the services that a sensor node provides.
- 2) **Network Faults:** Routing is one of the fundamental building blocks in WSN. Faults on the routing layer can lead to dropped messages or unacceptable delays. There are highly unstable communication links that connect nodes of WSNs together. Radio interference can also cause the link between nodes to become faulty. Another source of link failure is the collision of messages in close proximity due to a phase change and overlap. In some situations, however, nodes may have perfect link connections but the messages may not be delivered to their destination due to path errors.
- 3) **Sink Faults:** On a higher level of the network is the sink node or processing elements that collects all the data generated in the network and propagates it to the back-end system. When the connected nodes fail without any existing fault tolerance capacity, there is high tendency of gross network failure since acquired data from the individual nodes can no longer be accessed [7].

Mobile agent integrated algorithm offers to be an effective and efficient model that can adequately reduce the existing data traffic in wireless sensor network because of limited communication ability of the network [8].

2.2 Clustering in Wireless Sensor Networks

There are many cluster-based routing protocols in wireless sensor networks in published literature [9;10]. In cluster-based routing protocol, the idea is to group the nodes that are closed to one another into clusters. The idea is to select a sensor node as the cluster head (CH) in each cluster. Cluster members directly sends the acquired data to its serving CH. Cluster heads have the responsibilities of aggregating and forwarding of the received data to the sink node either through single-hop or multi-hop transmission [11].

Clustering is the process of grouping the sensor nodes in a densely deployed large-scale sensor network. In the conventional set up, sensor nodes in any environment are configured to collect data and transmit it to a processing

element either directly or via other multiple hops in cases of large-scale networks. For scalability, robustness and reduced network traffic concerns, many sensor applications apply clustering technique to sensor nodes.

2.3 Faults in Wireless Sensor Networks

A fault is any type of fault that can result to an error. An error is synonymous to an undefined (incorrect) state of a system. Such incorrect state can lead to a failure. A failure is encountered if there is a notable error in the network, which happens when the network does not meet its requirements and is unable to perform its original tasks. Most sensor networks are deployed in hazardous environments which exposed the network to faults at different levels. Faults in wireless sensor networks escalate and such escalation compounds the failure level of the system. For example, a power failure of a node will lead to the failure of the entire node. If the failing node is along the routing path, the packets of neighboring nodes that transmit data through this path will not be delivered.

Clusters are formed for nodes within the cluster to transmit data through the cluster head to the processing element or base station through a one hop or multi-hop transmission. If for many reasons the cluster head experience any failure, forwarding of messages from the cluster head is thereafter truncated. Software bugs can also trigger the cluster head to forward incorrect information.

2.4 Review of Related Works

This section presents the research work related to fault tolerance in wireless sensor networks with mobile agents.

Clustering protocols have been widely applied to routing in WSN because of many benefits it offer, which include scalability, energy efficiency, lesser routing delay and avoiding loops in finding the route to the BS [12]. [13] highlighted a strategy for balancing the load of processing elements, which is carried out by binding the sensor nodes to the processing elements based on the number of nodes that belong to the cluster and energy quantity to be expended in the transmission of data by the processing element.

Clustering requires selecting a small number of nodes to serve as Cluster Heads (CH) in a dense deployment of sensor nodes. Organising a network in clusters is an approach used in many applications to extend the lifetime of the network. In particular, agent technology offers several approaches for the design and implementation of agent-based sensor applications. [14] proposed a two-phase distributed clustering algorithm called Low-Energy Adaptive Clustering Hierarchy (LEACH) for data routing in homogeneous sensor networks. In LEACH algorithm, nodes are randomly selected to become cluster head and the role of becoming cluster head is rotated among the nodes. The cluster-heads aggregate the data captured by the member nodes belonging to their own cluster in order to reduce the amount of information transmitted to the base station, and transmit the processed data to the sink node. [15] reported a load-balanced clustering algorithm with distributed self-organization for wireless sensor networks. The article presented a clustering algorithm for load balancing base on their density distribution, distance among the nodes and from the base station which makes it different from existing clustering algorithms.

[16] reported that single hop transmission mode is not suitable for large-scale application sensitive WSNs.

[17] presented an optimized clustering scheme that improves existing LEACH protocol by dynamically selecting clusters according to the residual energy of nodes. However, the evaluation was carried out only on static networks.

Client/server architecture transmit data from multiple sources to a destination however, in mobile agent paradigm, a task-specific mobile agent follows a predefined path to traverse the relevant source nodes to gather and disseminate them to a central processing location. [18] adopted the technique of changing the parent method to provide a fault-tolerant with extended lifetime sensors network by optimizing the choice of paths. The agents at the source nodes are responsible for selecting its parent node or the next hop to the sink during data dissemination. However, injecting mobile agents at every source node will defeat the idea of using mobile agents to reduce the network bandwidth most especially in large scale networks.

[19] highlighted a hybrid technique that harnesses the services of wireless communication, mobile agent features, and data aggregation, to provide the efficiency of traditional response path optimization techniques in mobile agent itineraries.

[20] proposed an adaptive solution to maximize network lifetime for data processing in WSNs. The sensor nodes in the network are organized into clusters using distributed multi-hop clustering algorithm. [21] reported that detecting faults and recovery of faulty nodes in wireless sensor network is a crucial task in order to guarantee the longevity of the network. The study demonstrated a fault recovery algorithm without providing an alternate route for data routing during occurrences of faults.

A distance vector routing protocol is proposed in [22]. The transmission distance between two nodes and the node's remaining energy are considered in the path selection of the protocol. The transmission distance enables high rate of successful transmission while the node's remaining energy guarantees load balancing. The adopted single-path routing strategy results to inequality in the nodes' energy consumption. There will be early energy drainage of nodes that belong to the same routing path which will eventually lead to early death of some nodes and therefore do not provide for fault tolerance property.

[23] proposed a protocol that CHs and cluster members are simultaneously decided in the clustering phase. Each node computes its time delay which is calculated based on the node's residual energy. Once the CHs are selected, other nodes choose their CH using a multi-objective optimization method that considers the CH's residual energy, distance of nodes from CH, and distance from CH to sink. However, the protocol has no control over the number of CHs to be created, it does not consider sensor nodes that do not belong to a CH and it is only fitted for a small-scale network.

[24] proposed a self-organizing fault-tolerance model for wireless sensor networks to be used for fire detection in conservation areas. This is achieved through self-interactions among neighboring nodes that are deployed to sense data within the same region. Wind, humidity and temperature data were considered as a set of decision trees for decision making for fire detection scenario.

[25] reported mobile agent based key distribution approach for clustered wireless sensor networks. In WSN, key management is very critical in protecting data and securing communications of collected data. However, the resiliency of the mechanism is not validated.

[26] reported the adoption of mobile agents for clustering in wireless sensor networks. The drawbacks of the current cluster-based routing methods include excessive energy consumption of the cluster heads due to additional processing loads on the cluster head. Placing the mobile agents in WSNs to act as cluster head can overcome the challenge of high energy consumption on the conventional cluster head. [27] conceptualized a mobile agent-based mode for efficient energy utilization in wireless sensor networks. The study adopted markov chain model to represent to represent the sensor nodes in the network. In the event of a cluster CH failure, all the active members are managed by a neighboring failure-free CHs. However, the approach does not distribute the fault tolerance load on the active neighboring CHs.

[28] formulated a routing itinerary scheme for multi-agent itinerary planning that guarantees energy efficiency in wireless sensor networks. The protocol works with the principle of minimum spanning tree. The major contributions of the study include, cluster formation to ensure that no two source nodes in the network belong to the same cluster, selection and construction of CHs, definition and planning of mobile agents' itinerary and subsequent migration of the agent.

[29] proposed a clustered routing approach to towards energy efficiency by using gravitational search algorithm to assign sensor nodes to an appropriate cluster head. The paper considered communication cost between member sensor nodes to CH and lifetime of CH for clustering. The number of CHs was selected based on the density of the nodes in a zone. [30] reported that proper selection of cluster heads plays a crucial role in prolonging the life time of wireless sensor networks. The paper adopted artificial bee colony algorithm for clustering protocol among the sensors. The protocol follows the path with sufficient energy level for data transmission. This strategy does not support sufficient life span of the network as the paths always utilize for data communication stand the chance of losing their energy earlier than the paths that are less utilized.

It is obvious from existing works that the challenge of maximizing the network life time in wireless sensors have not been exhaustively addressed without generating high network traffic. Therefore, the need to design protocols for wireless sensor networks that guarantees network services in the wake of failures or temporal disconnection. The mobile agent's integration into the cluster heads has the capacity to solve overwhelming data traffic, minimal energy consumption as the agents visit only the cluster heads inside of visiting all the member nodes of the network and local processing of data and the CHs.

3. METHODOLOGY

In this section, the principle of our proposed approach to achieve fault tolerance in clustered-based wireless sensor network is presented.

Clustering techniques are machine learning mostly unsupervised methods that can be used to organize data into smaller groups based on discovered similarities among the individual data items. A simple formal mathematical definition of clustering is as stated below.

Let $X \in R^{m \times n}$ be a set of items representing a set of points x_i in R^n . The goal is to partition X into K groups C_k such that every data belong to the same group are more alike than data in other groups. Each of the K groups are called a cluster.

Assumptions

The following assumptions were made in the model.

- i. The network comprised N sensors nodes deployed in square field.
- ii. The processing element is situated outside the network area.
- iii. Nodes are deployed randomly.
- iv. The base station location is pre-determined.
- v. The cluster-head nodes communicate with their parent cluster-head, and finally every cluster-head node will communicate with the base station.

3.1 Energy Model of a Sensor Node

Adopting and adapting the energy model of Heinzelman *et al.* (2002), the calculation of energy consumed in the transmission and receiving of B bits is given in equations (1) and (2).

$$E_{tx}(i, j) = \begin{cases} \alpha_{tx} + \varepsilon_{fs} D_{(i,j)}^2 \beta, & D_{(i,j)} < d_0 \\ \alpha_{rx} + \varepsilon_{mp} D_{(i,j)}^4 \beta, & D_{(i,j)} \geq d_0 \end{cases} \quad 1$$

$$E_{tx}(j) = \alpha_{tx} \beta \quad 2$$

where

α_{tx} and α_{rx} represent the energy dissipated in transmitting and receiving one bit respectively.

$D_{i,j}$ the distance between the node i and j

3.2 Mobile-Agent Cluster-Based Protocol

The fundamental idea is to use mobile agents to collect data from sensor nodes of a cluster and creating independent sets by dividing the member nodes in each cluster. The independent sets are successively activated such that there is only one active set in any given round $r \in R$.

Active set nodes will remain in their active state and while other nodes will maintain low-energy sleep state with a required level of percentage which the sink will provide when is requested by application task as modified in (Ahmed. et al., 2014). It is assumed that there is a satisfaction percentage for each node refer to as $s(i)$ which denotes the percentage ability of a node to satisfy any requested task based on its available memory space and the remaining energy defined as:

$$s(i) = \frac{e_i M + m_i E}{2ME} \quad 3$$

where

M maximum memory threshold

E maximum energy threshold

A cluster head selects its independent sets inside its cluster as $ch \in CH$ construct a set dn_j of nodes by choosing those nodes one after the other from a set of nodes of CH and checking if they can attain the satisfaction (rs) according to equations (4) and (5)

$$\left\{ \sum_{i \in dn_j} s(i) / |dn_j| \right\} \geq rs \quad 4$$

$$DN = \cup_j dn_j, 1 \leq j \leq R \quad 5$$

3.3 Energy Consumption

Sensing and forwarding of data to the cluster head consumes much energy in WSNs than any other operations that take place in the network.

At cluster heads level, energy is consumed during reception, data aggregation and forwarding of the aggregated data to the cluster head.

Mobile Agents

The emergence of mobile agents in WSNs has alleviated energy constraints in characterized by client-server model. The MA carries the processing function as a small code inside a packet sent from node to node.

The proposed approach involves the following phases.

- a. Partitioning the network based on geographical information; this phase will produce a set of partitions/clusters that guarantee the shortest paths among nodes in the same partition/cluster.
- b. Each CH is integrated with MA.
- c. Determining the itinerary that pass throughout the source nodes grouping of each mobile agents.

In our case, a graph G is created such that each sensor node is a vertex in the graph. The graph edge (u, v) that connects nodes u and v is assigned if $SM(u, v) > SM_{Th}$.

K-means clustering algorithm is adopted in this study. K-means is a classical algorithm widely adopted in WSNs.

Given n sensor nodes $S_i: i \in [1, 2, \dots, n]$ into k partitions $P_i \in [1, 2, \dots, k]$ ($k \leq n$) from k centres " C_j " chosen arbitrarily. This algorithm aims at minimizing the distance among the sensor nodes " S_i " within each partition " P_j "

$$\arg \min_p \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{i=1}^n |S_i - C_j|^2 \quad 6$$

where

$|S_i - C_j|^2$ is a distance measure among sensor nodes " S_i " and the partition " C_j "

Figure 1: Mobile Agent-Based WSNs Clustering

The mobile agents' activities begin when the base station dispatches the agents and ends when mobile agents return to the base station with the aggregated packets.

The mobile agent consists of ID, route information, data buffer and processing codes, in which data buffer mainly load the data distilled or fused data from sensor nodes.

Considering a mobile agent dispatched by the base station to acquire data from n source nodes. If S_{code} is the amount of the mobile agent processing code and S_{head} is the packet header size of the agent, and S_{ma}^0 is the agent size at the initial dispatching from the processing element. Then;

$$S_{ma}^0 = S_{code} + S_{head} \quad 7$$

The reduced data payload collected by the MA at each source node is represented as

$$R_1 = (1 - p) \times S_{data} \quad 8$$

Where

S_{data} is the size of raw data at a source node.

p is an aggregation ratio ($0 \leq p \leq 1$)

Since there is no data aggregation at the first source, therefore,

$$S_{ma}^1 = S_{ma}^0 + R_1 \quad 9$$

Data aggregation begins from the second source node to reduce the redundancy between the data collected in the source and the data it carries. Therefore, the MA size after it leaves the second source node is

$$S_{ma}^2 = S_{ma}^0 + R_1 + (1 - p)R_1 \quad 10$$

After visiting the k th source nodes, the accumulated data by MA is computed as

$$S_{ma}^k = S_{ma}^{k-1} + (1 - p)R_1 \quad 11$$

$$= S_{ma}^0 + [1 + (k - 1)(1 - p)]R_1 \quad 12$$

After visiting all the n source nodes, the MA has a size S_{ma}^n in the range $[S_{ma}^0 + R_1, S_{ma}^0 + n \times R_1]$

As the agents transit round the network, it collects and aggregate data. The following formula is used to calculate the aggregated data:

$$S^i = \sum_{k=1}^i R_k \quad 13$$

Assuming

$$S_{MA} = S_{buffer} + S_{fs} \quad 14$$

S_{fs} denotes the identification ID.

S_{buffer} is the data taken by the mobile agent.

To reduce the amount of data transmitted, data must be fused in data aggregation. In general, the data is only fused in cluster head. Moreover, S_{buffer} is limited. The fusion operation will be made on in-between nodes that can sense and forward the data to the processing element. Decision for data fusion is taken based on

$$S_{buffer(j)} = (S_{buffer(i)} + S_j)(1 - p_{ij}f_j) \quad 15$$

where

p_{ij} denotes the proportion of data reduction.

The decision on whether the data should be fused in node j or not is taken based on:

$$(p_{ij} \in [0,1]). f_j (f_j \in \{0,1\})$$

If $f_j = 1$, the data would be fused, otherwise, the data would not be fused.

The expected number of hops to complete the task or visit all nodes in failure, for a route $R = S_1, S_2, \dots, S_n$, is

$$H_{opR} = 1.P_1 + \sum_{i=2}^n (i. \prod_{j=1}^{i-1} (1 - P_j)P_i) + (n + 1) \prod_{j=1}^n (1 - P_j) \quad 16$$

4. DISCUSSION

The next phase of the study will be the implementation of the proposed technique with the following minimum requirements.

The initial energy level of each sensor node will be assumed to be at 0.5 joules. A node will be considered dead if its energy level is between 20 to 0 joules. The general simulation parameters are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Simulation Requirements

Parameters	Values
Simulation area	200m X 200m
Initial Energy	2J
Number of nodes	100-400
The threshold of energy consumption	0.01J
S_{MA}	500Bytes

S_{fs}	100Bytes
S_{Buffer}	400Bytes
Fusion factor	1
Reduction ratio (r)	Default (10%)
Topology configuration mode	Randomized

5. CONCLUSION

Wireless Sensor networks are sophisticated in their requirements and providing clustering solutions for them also requires adequate knowledge of its applications, limitations of the sensor nodes and the tradeoff among the expected performance parameters.

The objective of this article was not to design the best clustering topology for energy efficiency in wireless sensor networks considering that it requires a synergy among computer networks professionals in the development process. However, this can be considered as a step in achieving that.

Based on a general data aggregation model, we present a cluster-based cooperative data processing based on mobile agent algorithm that provides an alternative for the mobile agents to route the gathered data should in case there is a network failure during transmission and in response to environmental changes. Grouping of nodes into clusters reduces network traffic during the transmission of sensed data to the cluster heads.

With the idea of node clustering, the sensory ability of sensor networks for data gathering can be improved and the energy consumption for the MA migration can be balanced. Theoretical analysis shows that the proposed route algorithm that is fault tolerant reduces the energy consumption and transmission delay comparatively which will help to keep the network stability and prolonging the network lifetime.

The principle will also improve the energy preservation and reduce the task duration in WSNs.

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